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L13 Progress in broiler selection: benefits, limitations as assessed by the digestive function, and consequence on dietary lysine concentration.

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The results observed previously in the broiler lines genetically selected for high (D+ line) and low (D-) digestibilities were considered together with those observed in modern broiler strains. It was deduced from these comparisons that the selection for high meat yield in modern broilers was a major driving force explaining the evolution of their physiological functions. In modern broilers, the reduction of relative organ sizes resulting from the increased meat yield was at the opposite of what it should be expected from an increased feed intake. This paradox was made possible in modern broilers either by an increase in the efficiency of organs or by the disappearance of some functions, as assessed by the observations regarding intestine or gizzard, respectively. The relationships between daily feed intake (DFI), body weight (BW), daily growth, age and feed composition were precisely calculated using a computation model based on the analysis of 42 publications. For a 2.5 kg slaughter weight, it was calculated from this model that one day reduction in the rearing period produces linearly a 0.034 reduction in the value of feed conversion ratio. Thus, selection for increased growth rate is by far the most efficient way for improving feed efficiency in broilers. According to the model, the requirement for relative organ size, as assessed by the DFI/BW ratio, increases slowly compared with the daily growth change. This means that the consequences of an organ weight deficiency can be difficult or long to be perceived. According to the model, future progress in growth rate is associated with no change in protein efficiency, and with higher increase in feed lysine concentration than in the past for each day gained in the rearing period.

Keywords: broiler; genetic selection; growth; feed efficiency; meat yield; organ weight; digestion; model

Introduction

The genetic selection of farm animals for improved production yield has been very efficient for the last century, especially in animals with high reproductive rate such as broiler chickens. This improved production yield obtained in broilers came essentially from increased growth rate.

The growth rate of broilers is often assessed by the age at slaughter. Considering this slaughter age, it is obvious that a biological limit exists. It is very difficult to propose an age defining this biological limitation to growth rate. However, whatever this limit, it is probable that this limit will be reached according to an asymptotic process characterized by increasing difficulties when approaching this limit. Such difficulties have already been experienced by emerging physiological problems such as diseases regarding locomotion, and respiratory or

cardiovascular systems. Genetic progress reduced these problems by changing leg conformation and by applying specific selection against physiological syndromes such as ascites. Thus, these increasing difficulties could lead to the idea that the selection progress for more and more rapid growth should be stopped, because of increasing cost in the growth rate selection process. It is rather difficult to estimate this future increasing cost. However, the potential loss due to such a stop can be quantified by determining the precise relationship between growth rate and production yield, deduced from the literature analysis. The literature analysis can also be used to understand the origins of limitations to improved growth rate, in order to facilitate progress in growth rate selection.

Such literature analyses are performed in the present review. We report first the analysis of broiler selection limitations as assessed by the digestive function. The second part is especially devoted to feed intake, as the production yield in broilers is often assessed by the [(body weight gain) / (feed intake)] ratio, called “feed efficiency”, or by the [(feed intake) / (body weight gain)] ratio, called “feed conversion ratio” (FCR). Precise relationships between feed intake, body weight, body weight gain, age and feed composition were investigated by the development of a computation model based on the analysis of 42 publications. Using the feed intake prediction data, it was also possible to predict the feed lysine recommendations associated with increased growth rate.

Interaction between broiler selection and digestive functions: a model for a comprehensive approach of the selection consequences.

Digestibilities in growing chickens can be efficiently controlled by genetic selection, as previously reported with the D+ (high AMEn) and D- (low AMEn) lines selected for divergent AMEn value measured on a wheat diet (Mignon-Grasteau *et al.*, 2004; Rougière *et al.*, 2009; Rougière and Carré, 2010; de Verdal *et al.*, 2013).

As feed efficiency is a major factor involved in the development of commercial broilers, low AMEn values observed in commercial broilers compared with broilers from D+ line (Carré *et al.*, 2008) seem a paradox. A recent study (Carré *et al.*, 2013; unpublished) comparing D+, D- and Ross broilers showed that the AMEn value of a wheat (Rialto cultivar) diet measured at 4 wk was still lower ($P = 0.0001$) in Ross (3041 kcal/kg DM) than in D+ birds (3260 kcal/kg DM). However, the AMEn Ross value was closer to the D+ than to the D- value (2307 kcal/kg DM), whereas the reverse was previously observed (Carré *et al.*, 2008), which could mean that Ross digestibilities were improved during the last recent years.

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN ORGAN SIZE AND FUNCTIONS

D+ broilers were characterized by increased gizzard weight (Péron *et al.*, 2006; Rougière *et al.*, 2009; Rougière and Carré, 2010; de Verdal *et al.*, 2011) and reduced intestine weight (Rougière *et al.*, 2009; Rougière and Carré, 2010; de Verdal *et al.*, 2011) compared with D-

broilers. Moreover, digestibilities were observed to be positively related to gizzard weight (GW), and negatively related to intestine weight (IW) in D+ and D- broilers, and in broilers from commercial strains as well (Carré *et al.*, 2010).

These observations regarding organ weight raise the question of the competition between organ and muscle growths, as commercial broilers have been selected both on growth rate and muscle yield (Schmidt *et al.*, 2009). In our recent study comparing D+, D- and Ross broilers (Carré *et al.*, 2013; unpublished), digestive organ weights were also measured (Table 1). Again, GW related to body weight (BW) was higher in D+ than in D-, and, for IW, the reverse was observed (Table 1).

Table 1 Simple linear regressions† expressing Ln(gizzard weight) (g) or Ln(intestine weight)‡ (g) as functions of Ln(body weight) (Ln BW) (g) or Ln(daily feed intake) (Ln DFI) (g DM) with genetic effect in model.

Y variable	Ln Gizzard		Ln Intestine	
	Ln BW	Ln DFI	Ln BW	Ln DFI
Regression coefficient	0.43	0.18	1.08	0.72
D+ intercept	0.30	2.38	-3.73	0.43
D- intercept	0.00***	2.06***	-3.59***	0.44 NS
Regression coefficient	0.54	0.55	0.86	1.05
D+ intercept	-0.45	0.82	-2.24	-0.95
Ross intercept	-0.85***	0.35***	-2.25 NS	-1.21*
Regression coefficient	0.53	0.36	0.88	0.86
D- intercept	-0.72	1.23	-2.18	-0.19
Ross intercept	-0.80 NS	1.31 NS	-2.37***	-0.25 NS

*, **, *** $P < 0.05$; 0.01; 0.001: Statistical significance of difference between two intercepts.

† Twelve calculations were performed, corresponding to two organs (gizzard or intestine), two related variables (BW or DFI) and three populations (chickens from D+ and D- lines (both sexes), $n = 104$; D+ and male Ross chickens, $n = 124$; D- and male Ross chickens, $n = 124$). Measurements were done at 25 and 32d in chickens fed a wheat (Rialto cultivar) diet.

‡ Duodenum + jejunum + ileum

Considering Ross broilers, their digestive organ weights related to BW were always the lowest compared with D+ or D-, with significant differences ($P < 0.001$) in two cases among four (Table 1). This suggests that high meat yield was a major selection criterion in Ross broilers, pushing down the organ proportions.

In the case of gizzard, positive relationships between gizzard relative weight and digestibilities were previously observed in commercial broilers (Maisonnier *et al.*, 2001; Carré *et al.*, 2010) and in broilers from D+ and D- lines (Péron *et al.*, 2006; Rougière *et al.*, 2009; de Verdal *et al.*, 2011). Thus, the small relative gizzard weight of Ross broilers compared with D+ broilers (Table 1) would explain the diet AMEn value that was lower in Ross than in D+ broilers (see above).

In the case of intestine, the interpretation of reduced organ weight in Ross broiler is opposite, because reduced IW was observed to be associated with better digestibilities (Carré *et al.*, 2010; Rougière *et al.*, 2010; de Verdal *et al.*, 2011). Thus, in Ross broilers, the efficiency at the intestine level is probably high, which would compensate in part the low efficiency at the gizzard level and would result in AMEn values intermediate between D+ and D- birds.

Thus, in the case of digestive function, the reduction of relative organ weights associated with increased meat yield may result in opposite effects on efficiency, depending on the organ.

Accordingly, the reduction of organ relative weight cannot always be considered a negative factor, because such a reduction can be a sign of high efficiency allowing the body system to economically reduce the organ size. It is probable that, for many functions, Ross broilers evolved in such a way.

However, the efficiency of organs cannot be considered the only driving force of their size variations. Two other factors should also be considered.

The gizzard offers an illustration of the second factor, namely the function suppression (or reduction). The suppression (or reduction) of a function is possible for an organ when it does not affect the organism survival or when another organ can take over the function. Regarding the gizzard, precise observation of their functions in D+ and D- birds showed that the gizzard of D- birds lost its functionality (Rougière and Carré, 2010; Rougière *et al.*, 2012) and showed a possible bypass process by direct connection of inlet and outlet of gizzard (Rideau, 2014; personal communication). The gizzard function is probably not essential because enzyme hydrolyses remain limited and no absorption occur in it. Moreover, its function loss can probably be partly compensated by increased pancreatic secretions and increased intestine efficiency.

The low heart relative weight observed in modern broilers at 1kg BW (Schmidt *et al.*, 2009) could partly come from the suppression (or reduction) of a function, namely the emergency heart activity associated with extra events, such as physical activity (Corr *et al.*, 2003).

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN ORGAN SIZE AND DAILY FEED INTAKE

The third factor associated with the size of many digestive or metabolic organs such as intestine, liver, respiratory, cardiovascular or urinary systems, is obviously the throughput that the organ has to process, *i. e.*, the highest is the throughput, the highest should be the organ size. Such throughput may concern daily oxygen consumption, daily carbon dioxide production, daily glucose absorption, etc. Whatever the physical or chemical nature of throughputs, these throughputs are proportional to daily feed intake (DFI) in *ad libitum* fed animals. Thus, for a better comprehensive approach, organ weights should probably be related to DFI.

When comparing D+, D- and Ross broilers, IWs showed better similarities between lines when they were related to DFI instead of BW (Table 1), which suggests that intestine adjusted its weight according to a requirement defined by DFI. Combining all birds considered in the experiment shown on Table 1, a linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.76$; $n = 176$) was observed between IW and DFI, and the genetic effect added in the model was not significant.

Studies reporting relationship between organ weight and DFI seem to be very scarce. In most studies investigating organ growth, organ weight is related to BW. However, these latter allometric relationships can supply useful information. Schmidt *et al.* (2009) described allometric relationships in Ross broilers for two organs concerned with dependence to throughput, namely heart and intestine. From 2 to 35d, the allometric exponents were found to be 0.88 for heart, and ranged between 0.66 and 0.76 for intestinal segments (Schmidt *et al.*, 2009). These values were rather close to the allometric exponent calculated for DFI (0.72) in our model calculating feed intake in Ross broilers (see next chapter), which is in good agreement with the idea that, for organs depending on throughput, organ weight is practically proportional to DFI.

Unfortunately, DFI data were not clearly shown in the study reported by Schmidt *et al.* (2009). Therefore, we calculated these mean DFI values on the basis of mean BW values shown in the study (Schmidt *et al.*, 2009), using the classic feed compositions shown in Figure 2 for a 34d growth curve, by applying the model calculation described in the next chapter (α values of 14.4 and 15.5 for Ross 708 and UIUC lines, respectively). A linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.97$; $n = 12$) was observed between these calculated DFI values and the mean IW values supplied by Schmidt *et al.* (2009), with no significant effect of a line effect added in the model. On the contrary, the relationship between means of IW and BW was quadratic ($R^2 = 0.95$; $n = 12$).

Other previous results (Shanawany and Fahmy, 1988; Shanawany, 1994) analyzed in the same way as that described for Schmidt *et al.* (2009) (see above) led to the same observation: the relationship between gastrointestinal tract (GIT) weight and calculated DFI was linear, whereas the relationship between GIT weight and BW was quadratic.

So, it seems to be sound to consider DFI for explaining the organ size variations. Accordingly, feed intake is not only useful for the estimation of feed cost. It is also useful because it probably represents a physiological key factor associated with the size of many organs.

Consequences of increased growth rate on feed intake parameters and lysine recommendations

A MODEL FOR EVALUATING THE CONSEQUENCES OF GROWTH RATE CHANGES

In order to investigate the consequences of increased growth rates of broilers on DFI, we developed a model to compute DFI values on the basis of age, body weight (BW), daily weight gain (DG) and feed composition (AMEn, crude protein (CP)). The feed intake calculation allowed us to estimate also the feed lysine recommendations in relation to growth rate.

This model was developed using equations obtained from the analysis of literature data observed in 42 studies published from 1980 to 2013 (384 line file) reporting measurements of growth, feed intake, lipid and protein depositions in *ad libitum* fed broilers in standard temperature conditions (Table 2). In some of these studies, data were lacking for calculating protein efficiency (PE) and protein or lipid contents of gain (PCG or LCG). For these studies, it was necessary to estimate the initial body composition at the beginning of growth experiments (References n° 3, 5, 12, 22, 23, 26 in Table 2), the protein deposition as feathers in addition to protein deposition as plucked whole carcass (References n° 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 10, 15, 18, 19 in Table 2), or the whole protein deposition with a calculation from body growth (References n° 17, 30 in Table 2). These estimations were obtained according to data from other publications (Table 2), or from Larbier and Leclercq (1992) for feather associated corrections.

Table 2 References used for the regression computations predicting protein and lipid growth contents, and daily ME intake, in broilers *ad libitum* fed in standard temperature conditions.

N°	References	Trial s (n)	Treat- ments per trial (n)	Mean ages (days)	Sex	Grow th types *	Names of strains	Di ets per ass ay (n)	Ami no acid test
1	Leeson and Summers, 1980	2	4; 12	3; 10; 31; 38; 45; 52; 59; 66	1; 2	F	Unknown	1	No
2	Leclercq 1983	1	8	38	1	S	Fat; Lean	4	No
3	Whitehead and Griffin, 1984	3	6	24	1; 2	F	Fat; Lean; Unknown	1	No

4	Chwalibog <i>et al.</i> , 1985	1	6	9; 17; 25; 33; 41; 49	2	F	W. Cornish	1	No
5	Whitehead and Griffin, 1986	1	8	24	1; 2	F	Fat; Lean	2	No
6	Geraert <i>et al.</i> , 1987	1	4	38	1	S	Fat; Lean	2	Yes
7	Geraert <i>et al.</i> , 1988	1	4	35; 49	1	S	Fat; Lean	2	No
8	McLeod <i>et al.</i> , 1988	1	2	66	2	F	Fat; Lean	1	No
9	Chwalibog and Egum, 1989	1	4	32	1/2	F	W. Plymouth Rock	1	No
10	Geraert <i>et al.</i> , 1990	2	12; 10	38; 35	1	S	Fat; Lean	6; 5	No
11	McLeod, 1990	1	10	35	2	S	Unknown	10	
12	Morris and Njuru, 1990	1	5	11	1	F	Ross	5	No
13	Yu <i>et al.</i> , 1990	1	1	10	1	M	Hubbard	1	No
14	Leclercq and Guy, 1991	1	12	35	1	S	Fat; Lean	6	Yes
15	Leenstra and Cahaner, 1991	2	10	14; 35	1; 2	F	Fat; Lean; FC; WN; WI	1	No
16	McLeod, 1991	1	10	32	2	S	Unknown	10	No
17	Pinchasov and Nir, 1992	1	5	31	1	F	Unknown	5	No
18	Summers <i>et al.</i> , 1992	2	8	10; 32	1	F	Unknown	4	Yes
19	Geraert <i>et al.</i> , 1993	1	4	42	1	S	Fat; Lean	2	No
20	Leclercq <i>et al.</i> , 1993	1	10	37	1	S	Fat; Lean	5	Yes
21	Buyse <i>et al.</i> , 1994	1	8	9; 15; 20; 27; 35; 44	2	F	Hybro	1	No
22	Leclercq <i>et al.</i> , 1994	3	6; 8; 6	35; 35; 37	1	S	Fat; Lean	3; 4; 3	Yes

2 3	Deschepper and De Groot, 1995	1	10	24	1	F	Ross	10	Yes
2 4	Liebert, 1995	1	7	18	1	M	Lohmann	7	No
2 5	McLeod, 1997	1	5	34	1	S	Unknown	5	Yes
2 6	Nitsan <i>et al.</i> , 1997	1	4	35	1	M	Anak	4	No
2 7	Buyse <i>et al.</i> , 1998	1	8	26d 33; 40; 47	1	F	FC; GL	1	No
2 8	Buyse <i>et al.</i> , 1999	1	5	18; 21	1	F; M	A; B; C; D; E	1	No
2 9	Aletor <i>et al.</i> , 2000	2	5; 4	32	1	F	Lohmann	5; 4	Yes
3 0	Alleman <i>et al.</i> , 2000	2	6; 8	38	1	S	Fat; Lean	3; 4	Yes
3 1	Sanz <i>et al.</i> , 2000	2	3	32; 28	2	F	Hybro G	3	No
3 2	Aletor <i>et al.</i> , 2002	1	4	32	1	F	Ross	4	Yes
3 3	Carré <i>et al.</i> , 2002	3	10	28	1	F	ISA IJV915	10	No; Yes
3 4	Crespo and Esteve-Garcia, 2002	1	5	38	2	F	Ross	5	No
3 5	Noy and Sklan, 2002	1	9	4	1	F	Ross	9	No
3 6	Collin <i>et al.</i> , 2003	1	3	28	1	F	Cobb	3	Yes
3 7	Niess <i>et al.</i> , 2003	2	3; 2	32	1	F	Ross	3; 2	Yes
3 8	Fatufé <i>et al.</i> , 2004	1	10	14	1	F	Ross	10	Yes
3 9	Pym <i>et al.</i> , 2004	2	4	25; 38	1	F; S	QL; CL; Fat; Lean	2	No
4 0	Olukosi <i>et al.</i> , 2008	1	15	3; 10; 17	1	F	Unknown	5	No
4 1	Priyankarage <i>et al.</i> , 2008	1	12	16	1	F	Ross	12	Yes

4	Conde-Aguilera <i>et al.</i> , 2013	1	2	25	1	F	Ross	2	Yes
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*F: fast growing; M: medium growing; S: slow growing broilers.

Broilers were considered “fast growing” (Table 2) for the results published with commercial broilers from 2000, or for the mean [measured growth / calculated growth] ratios (R) above 0.75. Broilers were considered “medium” and “slow growing” (Table 2) for $0.5 < R < 0.75$ and $R < 0.5$, respectively. These calculated growth values were based on age according to Sakomura (2005).

Regression calculations were conducted with both “SuperAnova” (1989-1991, version 1.11, Abacus Concepts, Inc., Berkeley, CA, USA) and “R” (2013, version 3.0.2, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) softwares. Mean BW^i values were calculated as $[(\text{initial } BW^i + \text{final } BW^i)/2]$. A data was considered outlier when its absolute residual value exceeded 3RSD. Outliers were removed one by one by applying automatic iterative calculations.

The regression calculation expressing PCG (equation 2, see below) was performed with only male “fast growing broilers”, and only considering growth data above 90% of the control growth ($n = 159$; $R^2 = 0.506$; no outliers), with no introduction of trial effect in the calculation model.

The equation 3 predicting LCG (see below) was built according to 4 principles: 1-LCG values (g/g) show minimum of 0.025; 2-LCG values increase with increasing BW (Sakomura *et al.*, 2005); 3-LCG values decrease with increasing PE (Leclercq and Guy, 1991; MacLeod, 1997); 4- LCG values decrease with increasing CP/AMEn ratio (Fisher, 1984). This equation 3 was obtained in 2 steps. First, $[\text{Ln}(\text{LCG} - 0.025)]$ was calculated as a function of $\text{Ln}(\text{BW})$ using whole data (Table 2), with no introduction of trial effect in the calculation model, which produced:

$$\text{LCGc (g/g)} = 0.025 + 0.1373 \text{ BW}^{0.4176} \text{ (kg); } n = 357; R^2 = 0.33; 27 \text{ outliers}$$

Thereafter, the regression expressing $[\text{Ln}(\text{LCG}/\text{LCGc})]$ as a function of $[\text{PE}]$ and $[\text{CP}/\text{AMEn}]$ was computed using whole data, and with the introduction of trial effect (55 levels) in the calculation model ($n = 371$; $R^2 = 0.818$; 13 outliers), which led to the equation 3 bearing an α coefficient of 15.49. This α coefficient was the exponential value of the mean of the 55 intercepts specific to each trial ($P = 0.0001$). The value of 14.4 shown for Ross broilers (equation 3) was the mean of α coefficients assigned to Ross trials for obtaining equal trial mean values for the measured LCG and the LCG calculated with the model combining equations 1 to 5 (with a specific α coefficient for each Ross trial).

The equation 4 (see below), similar to those shown by Sakomura *et al.*, 2005), came from a regression calculation performed on whole data, and with the introduction of trial effect (55 levels) in the calculation model ($n = 365$; $R^2 = 0.959$; 19 outliers), the variables being

expressed as ratio to $BW^{0.7}$ (Noblet *et al.*, 2010). The $BW^{0.7}$ coefficient of 0.7204 appearing in equation 4 was the mean of the 55 intercepts specific to each trial ($P = 0.0001$).

The model for computation of daily feed intake and lysine requirement, based on age, feed composition, body weight and daily growth, was as follows for broilers:

A: age (day)

CP: Crude protein content (%) of feed

AMEnC: metabolizable energy value calculated from feed composition Tables

AMEnA: AMEnC corrected for age effect (after Zelenka, 1997 and Bourdillon *et al.*, 1990):

$$\leq 14d: \quad \text{AMEnA} = 0.93861 \text{ AMEnC}$$

$$> 14d, \leq 56d: \quad \text{AMEnA} = \text{AMEnC} (0.001465 A + 0.9181)$$

$$> 56d: \quad \text{AMEnA} = \text{AMEnC}$$

AMEn : measured AMEn or AMEnA (MJ/kg)

BW: Mean body weight (kg)

DG: daily weight gain (g)

PE: protein efficiency: protein growth / protein intake (g/g)

PCG: protein content of growth (g/g)

LCG: lipid content of growth (g/g)

MEI: daily ME intake (MJ)

DFI: daily feed intake (g)

$$(1) \text{ PE} = (\text{DG PCG}) / (\text{CP DFI} / 100)$$

$$(2) \text{ PCG} = 0.1242 + 0.00199 A - 0.0000264 A^2 + 0.4478 \text{ LCG} - 1.139 \text{ LCG}^2$$

(equation for male fast growing broilers)

$$A < 65d; \text{ LCG} < 0.3$$

$$(3) \text{ LCG} = \alpha (0.025 + 0.1373 \text{ BW}^{0.4176}) \exp(-2.090 \text{ PE} - 1.082 \text{ CP} / \text{AMEn})$$

$$\alpha = 14.4 \text{ (mean value for male Ross } ad \text{ libitum fed with standard temperatures)}$$

LCG < 0.3; BW < 3kg; 0.35 < PE < 0.70

$$(4) \text{ MEI} = 0.7204 \text{ BW}^{0.7} + 0.03075 \text{ DG PCG} + 0.04181 \text{ DG LCG}$$

LCG < 0.3; BW < 3kg

$$(5) \text{ DFI} = 1000 \text{ MEI} / (1.042 \text{ AMEn})$$

The computation consists in finding the values of 5 variables (PE, PCG, LCG, MEI, DFI) in a system of 5 equations (1, 2, 3, 4, 5), which can be solved with the Excel software (create a LCGf column with free values associated with columns expressing equations 1, 2, 4 and 5, and create a LCGe column expressing equation 3; LCGf are estimated by Excel solver so that LCGf/LCGe ratios are strictly equal to 1).

A and **B**: internal validation of the model, based on data from references of Table 2; predictions with an α value of 15.49 (see equation 3); **B**: measured and predicted values corrected for trial, genetic and sex effects (50 levels).

C, **D** and **E**: external validation of the model, based on Ross broiler data from references (Delezie *et al.*, 2012; Serrano *et al.*, 2012; Hashemipour *et al.*, 2013; van der Hoeven-Hangoor *et al.*, 2013 and Kim *et al.*, 2013) not used to develop the model; predictions with an α value of 14.4 (see equation 3) except for **E**; **D**: measured and predicted values corrected for trial effect (6 levels); **E**: predictions with adjusted α values (10.5, 16.2 (mash), 14.0 (pellets and crumbles), 12.7, 11.5 and 9.7, respectively).

Figure 1 : Daily feed intakes (g) in male fast growing broilers *ad libitum* fed in standard temperature conditions: relationships between measured values (Y) and values predicted

(X) with a model based on equations predicting ME intake, growth protein content and growth lipid content as functions of body weight, daily growth, age and feed composition (AMEn and crude protein) (see the text).

The computation of lysine requirement based on age, body weight and daily growth, is as follows:

LCPG: lysine content (g/g) of protein gain (after Larbier and leclercq, 1992)

$$\leq 14\text{d:} \quad \text{LCPG} = 0.061$$

$$> 14\text{d,} \leq 27\text{d:} \quad \text{LCPG} = 0.069 - 0.000596 A$$

$$> 27\text{d:} \quad \text{LCPG} = 0.053$$

DLR (daily digestible lysine requirement) (g) (after Boorman and Burgess, 1986):

$$\text{DLR} = 0.9 (0.082 \text{ BW} + 0.01486 \text{ DG PCG} / 0.173) \text{ LCPG} / 0.0603$$

$$\text{DLR} = 1.224 \text{ BW LCPG} + 1.282 \text{ DG PCG LCPG}$$

DFI and recommendations for feed CP and lysine contents are computed in a combined system, using known values for feed lysine to protein ratios.

Figure 1 shows comparison between the model computed DFI and the measured DFI values in male fast growing broilers, on the basis of studies shown in Table 2 (Figures 1A and 1B) that supplied the data for the model building. The α value (see equation 3) of 15.49 used in the model computation shown in Figure 1 is the α value obtained from the regression (equation 3) applied on all studies of Table 2. The effects of trial, genetic and sex were rather pronounced, as taking these effects into account reduced the RSD value by 57% with a value of 4.3g, which was rather low and acceptable.

The model was also tested with other recent studies that were not used for the calculation of model equations. Recent studies performed with only one broiler type (male Ross) were chosen, using an α value of 14.4 according to the results of the model run with the experiments of Table 2 conducted with male Ross broilers. Using this recent population, comparisons between the model computed DFI and the measured DFI values (Figures 1C, 1D and 1E) led to precisions rather similar to that obtained with studies of Table 2 (Figures 1A and 1B). The mean α value (12.4) found for these recent studies was somewhat lower than the mean α value (14.4) found for the male Ross studies of Table 2, which could mean that Ross selection continued to reduce fat deposition.

Actually, each specific population (sex and genotype) has its specific α value (see equation 3), as shown by the ratios of measured LCG to calculated LCG (equation 3 with an α value of

15.49). For instance, using studies of Table 2, the trial means for this ratio were 1.15 and 0.95 for males from fat and lean lines, respectively. The male chickens from fat line, lean line and meat fast broiler strains examined together in the same trials (Whitehead and Griffin, 1984; Leenstra and Cahaner, 1991) produced mean ratios of 1.45, 1.29 and 1.35, respectively, which shows that meat fast broiler strains were closer to the “lean” than to the “fat” type. In this way, the mean trial ratio found for male Ross broilers (Table 2) was rather low (0.88), which is in agreement with the idea that meat fast broilers are “lean” type chickens.

A broiler selection resulting in lean type chickens is consistent with a selection conducted for improved feed efficiency (Whashburn *et al.*, 1975; Whitehead *et al.*, 1984) and meat yield (Ricard *et al.*, 1982; Cahaner *et al.*, 1986).

FEED AND PROTEIN EFFICIENCIES ASSOCIATED WITH GROWTH RATE

The model calculation was run on past (2.5 kg slaughter at 56d), present (2.5 kg slaughter at 34d) and future growth curves (2.5 kg slaughter from 32 to 20d) (Figure 2).

From these calculations, it can be estimated that 30 years selection for improved growth rate (2.5 kg slaughter at 34d *versus* 56d) resulted in 50% improvement in feed efficiency (Figure 2). In comparison, a selection for leanness generally results in only 10% higher feed efficiency than a selection for fatness (Leclercq, 1983; Whitehead and Griffin, 1984; Leenstra and Cahaner, 1991).

However, according to the model calculation, the 34d instead of the 56d growth curve results in a rather low protein efficiency improvement (11%) (Figure 2). Probably, this improvement has to be attributed to the end of the finishing period of the 56d growth curve, characterized by a decreased growth rate associated with a feed intake that was mainly adjusted on lipid deposition requirement. The extent of this improvement is similar to a protein efficiency improvement obtained by a leanness selection instead of fatness (Leclercq, 1983; Whitehead and Griffin, 1984; Leenstra and Cahaner, 1991).

*The growth curve for a 2.5kg slaughter at 34d was deduced from an experiment performed with Ross Pm3 in 2013 (Carré *et al.*, 2013; unpublished). Other growth curves for 32 to 20d 2.5 kg slaughters were calculated using means of horizontal and vertical stretches of the 34d growth curve. The 56d growth curve was the curve described for male broilers in 1984 by INRA. The model was run with the starter (S), grower (G) and finisher (F) periods being the 40-350g, 350-1100g and 1100-2500g BW intervals, respectively. Moreover, model calculations were based on AMEn (chicken values) of 11.87, 12.46 and 12.86 MJ/kg for S, G and F, respectively, and a constant [digestible lysine/crude protein] ratio of 0.052. The α value used for the equation 3 occurring in the model (see the text) was 14.4.

Figure 2: Results of the model computations (see the text): daily feed intakes (DFI), total FCR and total protein efficiency (protein deposition/protein intake) (0day – 2.5kg slaughter day) for various growth curves in broilers*; allometric relationships between model calculated DFI and body weight (BW), and recommendations for digestible lysine feed concentrations calculated by the model.

In the future, a reduction of the 2.5kg slaughter age from 34d to 20d would continue to improve the feed efficiency by 51% (Figure 2). According to model results (Figure 2), the relationship between the FCR value and the 2.5kg slaughter day (Ds) is strictly linear (FCR = 0.034 Ds + 0.307). However, from the 34d to the 20d growth curve, the protein efficiency would remain constant (Figure 2).

LYSINE RECOMMENDATIONS ASSOCIATED WITH GROWTH RATE

Any change in the genetic features of broilers generally induces changes in feed composition recommendations. For instance, it was observed that lean type broilers need higher amino acid feed concentrations than fat type broilers (Leclercq *et al.*, 1993, 1994; Alleman *et al.*, 2000).

The model computations supply estimations of lysine feed recommendation changes induced by the growth rate genetic changes.

According to the model, the lysine recommendation does not show strict linear relationship with Ds (Figure 2). For instance, a reduction of Ds from 56d to 34d is associated with an increase in digestible lysine feed concentration (%) of 0.012 per reduction day, whereas, from 34d to 20d, this reaches 0.027 per reduction day (calculations for finishing period; Figure 2). Thus, in the future, amino acid recommendations would increase more than in the past at each day gained in the total rearing period. So, digestible lysine feed recommendations are calculated to be about 1.6% for starting and growing periods, and 1.4% for finishing period with a Ds value of 20 (Figure 2).

ALLOMETRIC RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN DAILY FEED INTAKE AND BODY WEIGHT

As the model computes DFI, it is also possible to calculate from the model the allometric relationships between DFI and BW (Figure 2). These relationships are important because they give the possibility to compare them to the allometric relationships between organ weight and BW.

Firstly, it can be seen from these relationships that great variation in growth rate is associated with small variation in the allometry of DFI. For instance, from the 56d to the 34d growth curve, the daily growth, for a same weight, is about 60% higher, whereas DFI, for a same weight, is about 18% higher. Thus, if it is assumed that organ weights have to increase in the same magnitude as DFI, the pressure on organ weight requirement is not very pronounced. This means that the consequences of an organ weight below requirement can be difficult or long to be perceived. Thus, a failing in organ weight requirement induced by a genetic selection probably needs several selection years before some consequences can clearly appear.

Secondly, the broiler selection resulted in decreased relative weight for many organs (Schmidt *et al.*, 2009), whereas the opposite should have been observed because the DFI/BW ratios were increased by the selection. These opposite evolutions were probably compensated by increased efficiencies for many organs, as suggested for intestines. However, year after year, the discrepancy between the evolutions of relative organ weight and DFI/BW ratios can be so pronounced that some disorders may appear because of no possibility of compensation by improved organ efficiency.

Conclusion

For a 2.5 kg final BW, we calculated that one day reduction in the rearing period produces a 0.034 reduction in the FCR value, which confirms that selection for increased growth rate is by far the most efficient way for improving feed efficiency in broilers.

However, growth rate was not the only factor selected in broilers. Improved meat yield was also selected, which resulted in decreased relative weights for many organs. Such decreases represent an important challenge for many physiological functions, because an opposite evolution of relative organ sizes had to be expected from an increased growth rate.

Thus, it is probable that the main factor responsible for the disorders which are sometime observed in broilers is the high meat yield, not the high growth rate. Thus, the progress in feed efficiency associated with increased growth rate could be impeded in the future if, in the same selection process, a strong selection pressure would continue to be applied on increased meat yield. It is not excluded that a small decrease in meat yield will be necessary in the future for obtaining a continuous progress in growth rate.

Better feed efficiencies obtained by higher growth rate will lead to reduced consumption of energy suppliers such as cereals or tapioca roots. However, this will not result in reduced consumption of proteins. Moreover, the need of protein sources with high protein concentration or well balanced amino acid composition will markedly increase. Accordingly, the introduction of pure amino acids in broiler diets will be more and more necessary.

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